

An insight to osseodensification.

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Abstract

Osseointegration as proposed by Branemark in 1969, is a primary determinant factor for assessing implant success. Osseointegration is a process in which a dental implant surface integrates and attaches to the ordered living bone. Primary stability is considered as the determinant factor to achieve a good osseointegration. Primary stability is affected by factors like the osteotomy techniques, local factors like bone density and volume, systemic disease like osteoporosis, diabetes mellitus, etc. Osseodensification is a novel procedure of autologous bone densification around dental implants, have been seen to enhance the initial stability to a very large extent. This review article will give an insight about the concept of osseodensification.

Keywords: Osseointegration, Osseodensification, Primary stability

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Introduction

Currently, dental implants are among one of the most preferred and popular treatment options for rehabilitating a lost tooth or multiple teeth. Dental implant success is dependent on the amount of osseointegration attained between the implant thread surface and the peri-implant bone. Primary implant stability is an important determinant of osseointegration. Primary stability depends on the type of bone i.e., bone density, the type of implant and surgical techniques. The insertion torque achieved during an implant placement helps to achieve the initial primary stability. A relatively newer notion of osteotomy known as osseodensification technique has emerged, in which the osseodensification burs work in a non-subtractive fashion, allowing simultaneous bone condensation as well as preservation through compaction of autograft during implant osteotomy site preparation in a circumferential outward direction [1]. Along with increasing the bone implant contact, it

also results in adequate amount of insertion torque and resultant primary stability. Osseodensification technique has been proved to be a boon in achieving in better osteotomy and bone densification. It can be effectively used in cases of indirect sinus lift and ridge expansion.

Primary and Secondary Stability

Branemark defined osseointegration as "a direct structural and functional connection between ordered, living bone and the surface of a load-carrying implant." Adequate primary or initial implant stability is a quintessential prerequisite criterion for a successful implant-bone osseointegration. Stability of a dental implant is measured by the anchorage quality between the implant and surrounding alveolar bone. Dental implant stability can be primary or secondary. Primary stability is said to be attained in the absence of any kind of micromovement of implant when it is in its totally seated position. This leads to mechanical

interlocking of implant threads into the surrounding alveolar bone until secondary stability is attained. Factors like bone density, Insertion Torque value, implant design and the surgical osteotomy technique influences the amount of primary stability. Due to inevitable surgical trauma during the osteotomy procedure, a minimum bone loss of 1 mm is seen due to devitalization, resorption, and remodelling of bone in the early phase of osseointegration affecting the primary stability. With the initiation of the osseointegration process within the bone-implant interface, bone gradually begins to grow increasing the bone to implant contact (BIC). The stability achieved at this stage is known as the secondary stability leading to a successful osseointegrated implant [1]. Secondary stability is seen to increase at four weeks after implant placement. At this point of time, the implant is least stable.

Concept of Osseodensification

Osseodensification technique helps in preserving bone by compaction of autogenous cancellous bone with non-subtractive drilling during the osteotomy procedure. In contrast to the conventional osteotomy procedures, osseodensification (OD) instead of excavating the bone, concomitantly compacts and autografts the cancellous bone debris in an outward and lateral direction. This not only performs the osteotomy but also preserves the vital bone tissue, improves the bone density and volume of the peri-implant bone. Specialized densifying burs, known as the **Densah burs**, were created to achieve this desired concept of bone densification.

Osseodensification has revolutionized the concept of surgical site preparation in implantology. Improved osteotomy site preparation along with bone densification in places requiring indirect sinus lifting and

ridge expansion can now be easily achieved by osseodensification. [2].

Increased insertion torque values achieved by placing an implant in a dense peri-implant bone, increases the primary stability of the implant along with initial bone healing, leading to reduced implant micromotion. In a study conducted by *Trisi P et al.*, stated that, higher values of insertion torque in denser bone had no correlation with development of bone necrosis or implant failure. [3]. In another animal study conducted by *Trisi P et al.*, they stated that, osseodensification procedure exhibited the ability to increase primary implant stability and maintain secondary stability. They further concluded that, osseodensification technique increased the bone volume percentage surrounding the implants, when implants were inserted in low density bone (D3 or D4), when compared to conventional implant drilling procedures. Densification of bone helps to avoid the bone sacrifice which is inevitable with traditional osteotomy procedures. They also concluded that, osseodensification procedure helps in expansion of bone in places with narrower ridge so that wider diameter implants can be placed effectively without creating any kind of alveolar bone dehiscence or fenestration [4].

Osseodensification (OD) procedure along with osteotomy simultaneously produces a condensed layer of autogenous graft along the body of the drill at sites with inadequate bone. The compacted, autologous bone has been shown to achieve increased primary implant stability facilitating osseointegration. Unlike conventional drilling procedures where bone remodeling requires a minimum of 3 months to heal, osseodensification (OD) technique requires lesser repair period of bone healing.

Densah Bur

Salah Huwais in 2013 tried to find an innovative method to preserve the healthy bone maximum during osteotomies, which prompted the idea of Osseodensification and fabrication of “densah bur” constructed by Versah® LLC company [5]. The main aim was to make space for the implant but losing minimum bone. This persuaded to develop a novel idea “Osseodensification (OD)” also named as “The Densah Technology by Dr. Huwais”

The densah burs function in two ways. It cut bone when rotates clockwise and densify bone rotating counterclockwise. The densah bur is made up in such a way that multiple flutes are present within a tapered geometry. It is also intended to produce a faster feed rate with minimum heat generation. Osseodensification is done by the flute back rake angle when it follows the anti-clock path. Besides that, rotating in counterclockwise helps to preserve and expand the bone for implant placement.

During the surgical procedure the diameter of the densah burs increase. Rotating at 800-1500 rpm in an anti-clockwise direction (OD) and clockwise direction (cutting mode) preserve and cut the bone respectively. [6]. The negative rake angle lands function in a non-bone cutting action.

Features of Densah Burs^[7]

1. The bur controls the expansion process while going deeper into the bone due to its conical tapered body.
2. At least one lip is included in the apical area that grinds bone rotating counterclockwise and cut bone rotating clockwise (Figure 1).
3. There are two faces in each helical flute- a burnishing face for burnishing the bone

and a cutting face in opposite direction for bone cutting.

4. An opposing reaction force acting axially, is generated when minimum one of the lips and lands is continuously rotating in a burnishing motion which results in a push-back phenomenon. Expansion procedure is induced by this phenomenon.

Working Principles of Densah Burs^[8]

1. Densah burs are composed of twist drills or straight fluted drills. Drills have 4 or more lands too direct them during the osteotomy procedure and helps compacting the bone (Figure 2).
2. Lands having large negative rake angle function as non-subtractive edges that increases the bone density. These burs work by expanding the bone during osteotomy and displacing the bone circumferentially to compact and compress. Thus, it increases biomechanical stability of implant.
3. The burs easily control the expansion process while going deeper into osteotomy site due to its cutting chisel edge and a tapered shank.

Mechanism of Osseodensification

In this procedure, the bone is deformed and expanded by the densifying burs in a control way and without losing any healthy bone tissue (Table No. 1). Due to the viscoelastic properties of bone, the osteotomy site diameter reduces-spring back when osteotome is removed. Residual strains created in the bone due to viscoelastic property helps to achieve bone compaction. Compressive force is created due to the residual strain against the implant, which promote osteogenic activity and finally helps in increasing bone implant contact and primary stability. Higher removal torque value generated with osseodensification,

occurs due to reverse compression of bone to implant. High insertion torque value indicates good primary stability. Overheating is eliminated by continuous irrigation. This irrigation fluids also help to impregnate the autograft bone debris on the surface of osteotomy.^[9,10]

Healing of the Osteotomy Site after Osseodensification

- Bone is granular at the crestal region. On the outer side the bone trabeculae show lamellar pattern and on the inner side, it shows granular pattern.
- In the coronal section, bone surface lined by osteoid bands is higher in percentage than other areas of the implants.
- Prominent increase in bone density in the most coronal area.
- Bone remodelling leads to bone apposition and increase in bone density instead of bone resorption^[4].

Advantages of Osseodensification

1. Compaction autografting and condensation: Preparation of osteotomy site with an undersized non-subtractive drill leads to lateral bone compaction which increases initial implant stability with improved insertion torque values and increased Bone-implant contact percentage.^[11,12]
2. Enhances bone density: In vitro testing by Huwais S and Meyer EG, concluded that these densah bur system allows preservation of peri-implant alveolar bone by condensation and lateral compaction of the autograft bone debris formed during the osteotomy site preparation.^{[13][14]}
3. Osseodensification procedure helps in expansion of bone in places with narrower ridge so that wider diameter implants can be placed effectively

without creating any kind of alveolar bone dehiscence or fenestration.

4. Increased residual strain: A rate dependent stress and strain as a result of bouncing motion (inward and outward) of the densah burs allows saline irrigation to pressurize the surrounding bone wall leading to increase in bone plasticity.
5. In a case report of Huwais S, he stated that, in places with inadequate bone quality and quantity, osseodensification helps to preserve bone bulk and promotes a shorter healing period for prosthetic restoration.^[15]

Limitations of Densah Burs

1. Due to lack of plasticity, being a non-dynamic tissue in cortical bone osseodensification method does not function properly.
2. Densification of Xenografts lack the viscoelastic property. So, they should be avoided for densification as they have only inorganic content providing the bulk.

Conclusion and Future Perspective

Implant osteotomy technique mostly involves removal of bone. As a novel osteotomy technique, osseodensification (OD) technique has been introduced recently that results in increasing implant stability. This method is seen to decrease the amount of inevitable bone loss that occurs with traditional drilling during osteotomy procedures. The idea of osseodensification (OD) has made a change in the conventional implant site preparation. It is seen that this procedure creates an expanded stronger osteotomy site for effective implant treatment, through bone compaction and autografting. It also increases bone mineral density, and the implant surface bone percentage. The healing process is also improved by conserving the bone. However,

studies found in the literature are inadequate to reach into any specific conclusion. Randomized controlled trials and long-term follow up studies are recommended for creating an evidence-based technique.

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FIGURES

Figure 1

Figure 2

TABLES

Table No. 1

Compaction autografting/ condensation
↓
Maintaining bone bulk results in higher Bone to implant contact (BIC)
↓
Enhance bone density
↓
Accelerates bone healing
↓
Increase residual strain
↓
Enhances osteogenic activity through mechanobiology
↓
Increase implant stability
↓
Higher insertion torque
↓
Implant stability Quotient (ISQ) reduces micromotion